

Titan Yellow Complexes of some Rare-Earth Salts

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Chlorides of Lanthanum, Cerium, Praseodymium, Neodymium, Samarium, Gadolinium, and Dysprosium react with titan-yellow to form yellowish brown coloured water insoluble complexes. They have been studied, in water at feebly acidic medium of 6.5-pH, by direct and reverse conductometric titrations, isolated and analysed.

EXPERIMENTAL

The oxides of La, Ce, Pr, Nd, Sm, Gd, and Dy (Chemistry Division, Bhabha Research Centre, India Product) were converted into chlorides by evaporation with hydrochloric acid. (A.R. BDH grade). Titan yellow (BDH grade) was dissolved in water to make 0.01 M solution. The rare-earth salts solutions were prepared as mentioned in earlier works¹. The pH of water used was adjusted by the addition of requisite quantity of dil.HCl.

Philips Conductivity-Bridge model (PR 9500) was employed for conductometric titrations. Both direct and reverse titrations were carried out in all these cases. The concentrations of the solutions used were of the order of $0.5-1 \times 10 M^{-3}$ to $0.5-1 \times 10 M^{-2}$.

TABLE I
Titan yellow complexes with Rare-earth Salts

Complex	Results of Analysis					
	Metal%	C%	H%	N%	S%	Cl%
1. Lanthanum $La(H_{19}C_{28}S_4N_5O_6)Cl, \%$	16.84 (16.87)	40.76 (40.80)	2.31 (2.30)	8.46 (8.50)	15.07 (15.54)	4.28 (4.32)
2. Cerium $Ce(H_{19}C_{28}S_4N_5O_6)Cl, \%$	16.94 (16.98)	40.71 (40.75)	2.31 (2.30)	8.45 (8.49)	15.43 (15.52)	4.28 (4.30)
3. Praseodymium $Pr(H_{19}C_{28}S_4N_5O_6)Cl, \%$	17.10 (17.08)	40.61 (40.70)	2.30 (2.30)	8.43 (8.48)	15.46 (15.50)	4.28 (4.30)
4. Neodymium $Nd(H_{19}C_{28}S_4N_5O_6)Cl, \%$	17.29 (17.38)	40.48 (40.55)	2.30 (2.29)	8.41 (8.44)	15.41 (15.45)	4.27 (4.28)
5. Samarium $Sm(H_{19}C_{28}S_4N_5O_6)Cl, \%$	17.94 (17.97)	40.13 (40.26)	2.28 (2.27)	8.37 (8.38)	15.31 (15.34)	4.25 (4.25)
6. Gadolinium $Gd(H_{19}C_{28}S_4N_5O_6)Cl, \%$	18.64 (18.65)	39.86 (39.92)	2.25 (2.25)	8.30 (8.31)	15.18 (15.21)	4.20 (4.21)
7. Dysprosium $Dy(H_{19}C_{28}S_4N_5O_6)Cl, \%$	19.10 (19.13)	39.61 (39.69)	2.23 (2.26)	8.25 (8.26)	15.03 (15.12)	4.18 (4.19)

Figures in the parentheses indicate calculated values.

1. Jamil Ahmad, Naseer Ahmad and S. M. F. Rahman, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **44**, 444.

0.01 *M* solutions of titan yellow and a rare-earth salt (La, Ce, Pr, Nd, Sm, Gd, and Dy) in water were mixed in equal proportion and the precipitate thus obtained was separated by centrifugation, washed with water and alcohol, dried over quicklime in vacuum and analysed. The analytical data on carbon, hydrogen, nitrogen and sulphur were obtained through the courtesy of Australian Micro Analytical Service, Melbourne, Australia. For the analysis of the metal the complex was fused with fusion mixture in a platinum crucible, the melt was dissolved in dilute hydrochloric acid and the rare-earth metal estimated². For the estimation of chloride the melt as above was dissolved in dilute nitric acid and the chloride was estimated as silver chloride. The analytical results are given in Table I.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Titan yellow form 1 : 1 complexes with the chlorides of La, Ce, Pr, Nd, Sm, Gd, Dy which is substantiated by the result of both direct and reverse conductometric titrations. On the basis of the analytical results the formula may be suggested as $(C_{28}H_{19}S_4N_5O_6)_MCl$ where *M* stands for the rare earths.

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2. J. F. Spencer, 'The metal of the rare-earth'. Longmans, Green and Co., London, 119, pp. 105-6.